

Influence of Leadership Styles on Outcomes among Private Organisations in Bangladesh

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Abstract

Background: The current study investigates how different leadership styles affect leadership efficacy, specifically in encouraging organisational success.

Methodology: This quantitative study used a descriptive survey research design and collected data from 305 full-time employees in private companies in Bangladesh. It applied structural equation modelling (SEM) as a data analysis method.

Results: The results show that transformational and transactional leadership approaches improve leadership outcomes. Contrarily, in the case of laissez-faire leadership styles, the study shows no discernible impact on leadership effectiveness.

Conclusion: The study adds to the evidence affirming the contextual nature of leadership. Specifically, our analyses demonstrate that transformational and transactional leadership approaches improve leadership outcomes.

Unique Contribution: This study presents significant empirical evidence about the influence of leadership styles on leadership outcomes.

Recommendation: The present study suggests that human resource managers and senior management can benefit from its guidance in implementing an effective leadership style that fosters employee engagement and work satisfaction.

Keywords: Leadership outcomes, private organisation, employee motivation, leadership types

Introduction

The modern business paradigm has significantly shifted from tangible products to ideas and mechanical competencies to literacy abilities. As a result, developing effective and dynamic organisational structures has become essential in the modern corporate environment, characterised by global markets, competition, technology, innovation and other political and social factors (Cortellazzo et al., 2019; Rijal, 2010). The dynamic business settings in which organisational leaders operate encompass various components, including diverse governance structures, accountability frameworks, and the management of production, distribution, and services, necessitating informed leaders to address evolving needs (Islam et al., 2024; Selvarajah et al., 2018; Avolio et al., 2003). Avolio and colleagues (2003) contend that enterprises are increasingly integrated with and exposed to the global marketplace. Consequently, it is essential to comprehend its ramifications for leaders' performance and their approach to the challenges posed by globalisation. Consequently, contemporary organisations necessitate astute administrators who comprehend the intricacies of the constantly evolving global landscape. This understanding is essential, especially for organisational leaders in developing countries like Bangladesh.

The Bangladeshi labour market, unlike many of its Western counterparts, is characterised by a growing need for competitiveness, growth, and sustainability within a variety of constraints (such as mismanagement, corruption, informal employment, political instability, bureaucratic complexities and a lack of resources), making efficient and dynamic leadership essential (Selvarajah et al., 2018; Uddin et al., 2017; Mozammel & Han, 2016). Nevertheless, with 164 million inhabitants, Bangladesh is a large consumer society experiencing significant transformations in the industrial and business sectors, transitioning from conventional to modern management practices (Sultana et al., 2024; Islam et al., 2023). While effective and dynamic leadership is essential in any business setting, its investigation within the Bangladeshi context is underresearched, necessitating the present study.

Thus, the primary objective of this research is to expand the present literature on many aspects of leadership effectiveness, which is essential for organisational development and optimum success. This research can establish a basis for further refinement by expanding upon the current understanding of the efficacy of various leadership styles and elucidating the underlying processes, contextual influences, prerequisites, and dynamics of the phenomenon in question. This research has the potential to address the literature gap, as most previous research on the effectiveness of leadership styles has concentrated on highly industrialised nations. In contrast, the current research exclusively focuses on emergent economic nations from developing countries, such as Bangladesh. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no study has been conducted to validate the multifactor leadership questionnaire scale (MLQ-5X), the managers' leadership styles, or the impact leadership style based on the MLQ-5X in the context of Bangladesh. So, this research is an effort that will initiate the milestone to bridge the gap in the literature.

Literature and theoretical overviews

Researchers, theorists, and commercial enterprises study leadership because it improves individual and institutional performance (Dimitrov & Darova, 2016; Davies et al., 2001). Dimitrov and Darova (2016) suggest that diverse conceptualisations of leadership and attempts to define it can also be inferred from various approaches. For example, some theories see leadership as a characteristic or approach, while others see it as a relationship. Leadership is how a manager or leader persuades employees to meet organisational objectives (Bass &

Avolio, 1994). According to Burns (1978), leadership is a process that involves motivating and enlisting others to accomplish lofty objectives. This study, however, looks at how interactions between leaders and subordinates shape the phenomena of leadership. This is in opposition to the distinctive approach, which maintains that a leader is the only source of leadership (see more Yukl, 2006). Our theoretical assumption suggests that both managers and employees participate in the leadership process in which leadership is observable through what leaders do or how they behave and that it can be learned (Koya et al., 2015).

This study aims to ascertain how supervisors' leadership philosophies affect their subordinates' perceptions of the efficacy of their leadership styles, as well as their degree of contentment with them and willingness to put in extra effort. With this objective in mind, the following research question is posed: What effects do different leadership styles have on extra effort and satisfaction from subordinates, and how do they differ in effectiveness as seen by the subordinates? From various leadership styles that can be investigated, three leadership philosophies, namely transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire, have been selected for analysis in the current study (see Figure 1). Furthermore, Table 1 displays multiple dimensions corresponding to the various leadership styles. For example, the transformational leadership style comprises five dimensions, whereas the transactional leadership style includes three.

Figure 1: *Theoretical model of the study*

Transformational Leadership Style

The concept of transformational leadership was first highlighted by Burns (1978) and was further elaborated upon by Bass and Avolio (2004). Transformational leaders intellectually encourage and motivate their followers, create enthusiasm among them, and are personally considerate of their followers' interests (Bass & Riggio, 2010). According to Tajasom and colleagues (2015), transformational leadership also plays a practical part in the success of any organisation. Transformational leaders encourage their followers by influencing their beliefs and values beyond the exchange and reward scheme. This type of leadership is one of the most successful ways for leaders to develop an emotional bond with their followers. The transformative leader greatly enhances employees' trust and respect for their leader. Employees are highly motivated by transformational leaders' vision because of their overwhelming appeal (Dimitrov, 2015). The following five dimensions of transformational leadership have been posited by Bass (1998).

The dimension of idealised traits has two divergent aspects: The first trait is "Idealized influence behaviour," which is associated with the social personality of the leader. The other is "Idealized influence attributes," which are attributes linked to features ascribed to the leader by their followers (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Leaders exhibiting idealised behaviours and

attributes obtain the trust and respect of their employees. They cautiously try to fulfil employees' demands and prefer their interests and needs over their own (Harms & Crede, 2010). *Inspirational motivation* engages subordinates to achieve goals by overcoming challenges and visualising a better future for their employment and business. Transformational leaders inspire innovation, energy, and creativity in their subordinates through intellectual stimulation. Leaders also question and evaluate every situation to promote creativity and innovation in subordinates (Bass & Avolio, 1994). *Individualised consideration* is another significant dimension of a transformational leader. Such leaders consider every employee by giving due attention to their progress and development, as Harms and Crede (2010) noted.

Transactional Leadership Style

Burns (1978) distinguished between transactional and transformational leadership, in which the leaders deploy various strategies to compel and inspire their followers to follow them. Both leadership styles offer unique strategies for appealing to employees' emotions and moral principles, making them engage research subjects in an educational setting (Nguni et al., 2006). By providing individuals with competitive perks and developing their creativity and dynamic nature, transactional leaders successfully manage the programmes and concerns within their organisation. Transactional leadership encompasses three principal dimensions: Contingent Reward, Active Management-by-Exception, and Passive Management-by-Exception (Bass, 1998).

The leader rewards subordinates for meeting goals in the contingent reward exchange paradigm. Transactional leaders commit to rewarding subordinates for achieving goals and following their promises (Nguni et al., 2006). Although leadership studies note that transformational leadership is more effective at motivating, inspiring, and satisfying subordinates for growth and development, the ideal leadership style depends on the organisation and culture.

Transactional leadership includes active and passive management by exception. Leaders use management by exception to change their behaviour based on subordinate interactions (Bass & Avolio, 2004). They add that the leader's interference is critical. A leader who routinely watches a subordinate's performance and behaviour notices differences, points out mistakes, and takes corrective action. Dynamic leaders observe their subordinates' behaviour, predict problems, and act before they arise.

Laissez-faire Leadership Style

A laissez-faire leadership approach involves little to no intervention work on the followers. Workers can apply their judgment and problem-solving skills without holding the leader accountable (Agotnes et al., 2021). According to Bass and Avolio (2004), laissez-faire leadership is the avoidance of intervention, the absence of leadership, or both. Generally speaking, laissez-faire leadership (avoiding) entails no interactions or agreements with followers. In this leadership style, decisions are often delayed, and no attempt is made to understand and satisfy followers' needs or motivate them. Similarly, according to Lewin et al. (1939), laissez-faire leadership is a type of leadership in which the leader has been chosen and is still physically in charge of the organisation but has primarily renounced the duties and obligations delegated to him or her. While some studies have proven this leadership style as fruitful, most research emphasises its drawbacks. Laissez-faire leadership promotes workplace stress and conflict (Glambek et. al., 2018).

Perceived Outcomes of Different Leadership Styles

Different leadership philosophies influence employees' attitudes and behaviours in different ways, either directly or indirectly. Previous research shows that whereas the transformational

leadership style has good connections with outcome factors, the transactional leadership style usually hurts long-term performance. Transformational leadership favours employee motivation, self-efficacy, additional effort, and organisational success (Kim & Yoon, 2015). For instance, Saleh's (2017) research demonstrates a connection between transformative leadership, contingent rewards, and leadership outcomes.

However, applying a particular leadership style can significantly impact leadership outcomes. This new study examines leadership results based on effectiveness, extra effort, and satisfaction. Leadership effectiveness shows whether subordinates think leaders are influential in their interactions at various organisational levels. Many studies show that transformational and transactional leaders are more effective (Yahaya & Ebrahim, 2016). The following hypothesis is developed to test a similar link in Bangladeshi setting and to demonstrate worldwide applicability.

H1 (a-c): Different leadership styles (e.g., transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire) positively affect leadership effectiveness.

Figure 2: Pictorial view of the hypotheses H1 (a-c)

The research indicates that group performance and goal achievement correlate with the leader's leadership style, directly influencing employee behaviour. It compels individuals to exert additional effort at work and perceive their supervisors as competent (Bass & Avolio, 2004). The research indicates that transformational leadership substantially influences followers' desire to put in additional effort at work. This further proves that when followers expend more significant effort than necessary, productivity rises, enhancing the organisation's performance. Morris (2009) notes that extra effort means employees' devotion to doing extra work to attain success and giving time beyond expectation for the success of an organisation. Bass (1985) illustrates that transformational leaders motivate their employees to exert additional effort and engage fully in their tasks. In contrast, transactional leadership, mainly passive management-by-exception and laissez-faire leadership, adversely affect employees' willingness to invest extra effort (Barnett, 2019). The following hypothesis is generated to examine such an association.

H2 (a-c): Different leadership styles (e.g., transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire) significantly influence the employees' exertion of extra effort at work.

Figure 3: Pictorial view of the hypotheses H2 (a-c)

Several studies have shown that a leader's style significantly impacts subordinates' satisfaction (Barnett, 2019). People's level of contentment with their leader's actions and the efficacy of their leadership approaches are measured by satisfaction. Vries and colleagues (1998) maintain that a more human-centred leadership style increases employee work satisfaction. Similarly, research by Packard and Kauppi (1999) reveals that different leadership styles result in varying degrees of job satisfaction. For example, leaders are happier when they get along well with their subordinates. Support and acknowledgement of leaders also increase the job happiness of subordinates. Based on the discussion above, the following theory examines this association in Bangladeshi private organisation contexts.

H3 (a-c): Employees' level of satisfaction is positively associated with the different leadership styles (e.g., Transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire).

Figure 4: Pictorial view of the hypotheses H3 (a-c)

Method and Materials

Sample

The current study used a quantitative methodology to analyse the impact of various leadership styles on subordinates' work satisfaction, additional effort, and perceived effectiveness. The sample comprised 305 full-time employees working in private organisations in Dhaka, the capital of Bangladesh. A survey was conducted to collect data from the designated population, irrespective of occupation, marital status, economic condition, religion, or gender. The exclusion criteria included part-time or informal employees and anyone with less than two years of work experience in their respective firms. Dhaka was chosen as the study location because of its high concentration of workplaces and status as Bangladesh's primary economic hub. Bangladesh is an emerging industrial nation with the 34th largest economy in the world.

Hence, leadership challenges within the private sector are crucial to examine. Consequently, it is necessary to examine how an effective leadership style enhances followers' motivation and happiness, thereby fostering a robust organisational culture that facilitates business progress.

Measuring Instruments

The survey used for this study has two parts. Section one contains socio-demographic data, whereas section two covers assessed variables. MLQ 360 (MLQ-5X) by Bass and Avolio (1994) examined subordinates' perceptions of diverse leadership styles that may affect their satisfaction, effort, and effectiveness. A revised MLQ (Bass & Avolio, 1994) assessed transformational, transactional, and laissez-faire leadership in Bangladeshi private businesses. The MLQ has 45 items on a five-point Likert scale from 0 (not at all) to 4 (often). Twenty of these focus on transformational leadership across five behavioural dimensions: Idealized Influence Attributes, Idealized Influence Behavior, Inspirational Motivation, Intellectual Stimulation, and Individual Consideration. The 12 questions assessed transactional leadership in three behavioural areas: Contingent Reward (4 items), Management-by-Exception Active (4 items), and Management-by-Exception Passive (4 items). Four factors evaluate Laissez-Faire Leadership, the third type. The MLQ measures leadership styles' effects on employees' extra effort (3 items), effectiveness (4 items), and satisfaction (2 items).

Data Collection and Analysis

We selected a quantitative study to evaluate the correlations between leadership styles and subordinate performance. A purposive sample was utilised to deliver a link to an online survey (Google Form), including structured questions, to around 450 respondents through email and social media platforms (e.g., Facebook, Messenger, WhatsApp, etc.). A total of 305 valid questionnaires were returned by respondents, yielding a response rate of 67.78%, and were then analysed. Participants were directed to complete the survey without the presence of their employer or supervisor to enhance the anonymity and confidentiality of the data. Furthermore, they were directed to refrain from disclosing any personally identifiable information on the survey, including their name or job identification number. After concluding the field survey and data collection, the results were uploaded to a computer for statistical analysis.

Findings of the Study

Participants' Demographics

The participants were comprised of 59% men and 41% women. Ages ranged from 20 to 44 and beyond, with the highest age group falling between 24 and 31 years old (49.5%). Most of them, or 49.5%, have a bachelor's degree, while 35.1% have a master's degree. Participants with 2-4 years of work experience in their respective organisations comprise the majority (58.4%) of respondents.

Instrument Reliability and Validity

The data's reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, rho_Alpha and composite reliability (CR). Hair et al. (2006) suggested that the composite reliability, rho_A, and Cronbach's alpha values should be more than 0.70 for the data to be reliable. Table 1 demonstrates that the composite reliability (CR) and rho A values are more significant than 0.7, indicating that the data are sufficiently reliable. **Table 1: Construct's Reliability and Validity**

Constructs	Measurement Items	Factor Loadings	Reliability			Validity AVE
			Cronbach's Alpha	Rho_A	R	

Laissez-faire Leadership (LFL)	LFL_1	0.948	0.851	0.957	0.879	0.71
	LFL_3	0.852				
	LFL_4	0.712				
Leadership outcome (Extra Effort)	OUT_EE_1	0.743	0.752	0.763	0.812	0.593
	OUT_EE_2	0.727				
	OUT_EE_3	0.784				
Leadership outcome (Effectiveness)	OUT_EF_1	0.797	0.819	0.819	0.881	0.649
	OUT_EF_2	0.764				
	OUT_EF_3	0.754				
	OUT_EF_4	0.738				
Leadership outcome (Satisfaction)	OUT_SA_1	0.801	0.794	0.804	0.906	0.828
	OUT_SA_2	0.747				
Transformational Leadership (TFL)			0.943	0.944	0.948	0.581
Individual Consideration (IC)	TFL_IC_1	0.785	0.798	0.808	0.869	0.624
	TFL_IC_2	0.701				
	TFL_IC_3	0.831				
	TFL_IC_4	0.835				
Idealized Influence (Attributes) (IIA)	TFL_IIA_1	0.841	0.808	0.814	0.875	0.636
	TFL_IIA_2	0.83				
	TFL_IIA_3	0.727				
	TFL_IIA_4	0.787				
Idealized Influence (Behavior) (IIB)	TFL_IIB_1	0.755	0.746	0.75	0.84	0.568
	TFL_IIB_2	0.768				
	TFL_IIB_3	0.798				
	TFL_IIB_4	0.703				
Inspirational Motivation (IM)	TFL_IM_1	0.792	0.799	0.801	0.869	0.624
	TFL_IM_2	0.756				
	TFL_IM_3	0.818				
	TFL_IM_4	0.792				
Intellectual Stimulation (IS)	TFL_IS_1	0.809	0.816	0.819	0.879	0.645
	TFL_IS_2	0.849				
	TFL_IS_3	0.786				
	TFL_IS_4	0.766				
Transactional Leadership (TSL)			0.849	0.861	0.877	0.579
Contingent Reward (CR)	TSL_CR_1	0.837	0.818	0.821	0.881	0.649
	TSL_CR_2	0.843				
	TSL_CR_3	0.819				
	TSL_CR_4	0.717				
Management By Exception (Active) (MBE_A)	TSL_MBE_A_1	0.767	0.787	0.79	0.862	0.61
	TSL_MBE_A_2	0.783				

	TSL_MBE_A_3	0.775				
	TSL_MBE_A_4	0.799				
Management Exception (Passive) (MBE_P)	TSL_MBE_P_1	0.817	0.836	0.838	0.89	0.67
	TSL_MBE_P_2	0.837				
	TSL_MBE_P_3	0.822				
	TSL_MBE_P_4	0.796				

This study evaluates validity using convergent and discriminant methods. Sarstedt et al., (2022) recommend AVEs of 0.50 and factor loadings of 0.70 for convergent validity. Table 1 shows item loadings from 0.701 to 0.948 and AVEs from 0.568 to 0.71. Thus, the data satisfy convergent validity. HTMT and the AVE (FL-test) square root assessed discriminant validity. The square root of a construct's AVE must exceed its correlation with other constructs for discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2009). The square root of the AVE confirmed that the data discriminant validity for each latent idea was more significant than their correlations. All other inter-item correlations are below 0.80, demonstrating each construct's distinctness. Discriminant validity across reflective constructs is proved by an HTMT-test result below 0.90 (Henseler et al., 2015). According to the study, all HTMT readings were below 0.90. The criteria for discriminant validity are met.

Model fit indices

The model's goodness of fit is assessed using fit indices such as Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), d_ULS (Squared Euclidean distance), and d_G (the Geodesic Distance), Chi-square, Normed Fit Index (NFI), and Root Mean Square Residuals Theta (rms_Theta). An SRMR value less than 0.08 (Hu & Bentler, 1998) is considered a good fit. Lohmöller (1989) suggests that the closer the NFI value to 1 and the rms_theta value to zero, the better the fit. Table 3 shows the model's fit indices values. It reveals that the estimated model's SRMR is 0.056, NFI is 0.870, and rms_theta value of 0.023, indicating a satisfactory model fit.

Table 2: Model fit indices

Fit Indices	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.052	0.056
d_ULS	2.642	3.153
d_G	1.121	1.135
Chi-Square	1660.096	1677.400
NFI	0.860	0.870
RMS_theta	.0182	.023
Chi-Square/ df = 1.83		

Test of hypotheses

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was utilised to evaluate the hypothesised link between the variables based on the adequate fit of the measurement model. The research employs beta coefficients (β) and t-statistics to assess the relationship between constructs according to the conceptual model. Table 3 presents the results of hypothesis testing. Findings indicate that transformational and transactional leadership styles significantly impact positive outcomes in leadership performance. Transformational and transactional leadership enhance

the efficacy of leaders' actions and interactions, motivating followers to exert additional effort and increasing their satisfaction level. Consequently, hypotheses H1 (a-c) and H2 (a-c) are validated.

Conversely, laissez-faire leadership does not impact leadership effectiveness or subordinates' satisfaction. Though it encourages subordinates to go above and beyond, laissez-faire leadership has a detrimental impact. Therefore, H3 (a-c) is unsupported. This shows that followers do not think laissez-faire leadership works, which limits their efforts. The findings also demonstrate that laissez-faire leadership does not satisfy followers.

Table 3: Results of the hypothesis testing

Paths	Hypothesis	Beta	T	P Values	Supported
TFL -> OUT_EF	H1a	0.499	7.28	0.000	Yes
TSL -> OUT_EF	H1b	0.306	4.03	0.000	Yes
LFL -> OUT_EF	H1c	0.095	1.64	0.100	No
TFL -> OUT_EE	H2a	0.322	3.69	0.000	Yes
TSL -> OUT_EE	H2b	0.362	4.14	0.000	Yes
LFL -> OUT_EE	H2c	-0.193	3.89	0.000	No
TFL -> OUT_SA	H3a	0.513	6.49	0.000	Yes
TSL -> OUT_SA	H3b	0.218	2.57	0.010	Yes
LFL -> OUT_SA	H3c	0.067	1.07	0.283	No
Higher order sub-factors (transformational leadership)					
TFL -> TFL_IIA		0.881	54.84	0.000	Predictor
TFL -> TFL_IIB		0.883	56.65	0.000	Predictor
TFL -> TFL_IM		0.876	55.14	0.000	Predictor
TFL -> TFL_IS		0.883	57.68	0.000	Predictor
TFL -> TFL_IC		0.886	53.18	0.000	Predictor
Higher order sub-factors (transactional leadership)					
TSL -> TSL_CR		0.844	37.21	0.000	Predictor
TSL -> TSL_MBE_A		0.85	37.50	0.000	Predictor
TSL -> TSL_MBE_B		0.593	8.138	0.000	Predictor

Discussion

This research aimed to determine how leadership styles affect leadership outcomes. Leadership theory suggests that leadership styles positively affect organisational commitment, job satisfaction, and subordinate discretionary effort (Bass, 2010). However, prior experts have recommended more research to confirm this association. This study fills a vacuum in leadership literature by stressing that management leadership behaviours can influence subordinates, which increases effort and satisfaction. This study used the collected data to examine the resilience of the MLQ-5X factor structure and scales. This is helped by validity, reliability, and factor-loading statistics. The MLQ-5X had good psychometric properties, including a high internal consistency metric across the scales and subscales that met Cronbach's alpha at 0.70. Transformational and transactional leadership styles were analysed using CFA in the second

stage. The higher-order model fit well and showed acceptable links, supported by the transformational and transactional leadership scores.

The hypothesis tests show that transformational and transactional leadership styles significantly affect leadership outcomes. The findings suggest leaders' styles motivate subordinates to work harder. The leader's efficacy—defined by their interactions with others at various organisational levels—and employee happiness, such as subordinates' regular satisfaction with their leader's collaborative approaches, are also shown. These findings corroborate previous studies conducted in cross-cultural contexts (e.g. Widyawati, 2020; Yahaya & Ebrahim, 2016; Mester et al., 2003). In this regard, Mester and colleagues (2003) highlight that leadership directs subordinates to enhance their job satisfaction and exert extra effort by effectively implementing transactional leadership. Widyawati (2020) notes that employee commitment shows leaders' support for their growth and involvement. As expected, our study shows that transformational leadership engages employees better than transactional leadership.

Regarding transformational leadership, this study explored the substantial contribution of both idealised influence and individualised consideration to promoting subordinate satisfaction. Transformational leaders can encourage followers to choose corporate aims over their own interests. Our findings indicate that such leaders are typically enthusiastic and engaged. On the other hand, transactional leadership enables employees to perceive themselves as team members. Employees who believe they are a part of the organisation are viewed as more committed to their jobs and able to assist in accomplishing corporate objectives.

Laissez-faire leadership needed to connect with intended leadership outcomes. This supports earlier research showing no link between laissez-faire leadership and employee performance (e.g., Wu & Shiu, 2009). The laissez-faire leadership style allows subordinates to do duties without direct supervision, which is a significant drawback (Wu & Shiu, 2009). Laissez-faire leadership allows subordinates to make their own decisions, which can lead to poor performance and employee stress. Laissez-faire leadership has a negligible impact on employee happiness and outcomes, but we appreciate it and encourage more research. Laissez-faire leadership works with skilled, motivated, and independent group members.

Conclusion

The findings of this research have significant academic and policy implications on the impact of leadership styles on a leader's effectiveness and the attainment of follower satisfaction. The present study adds to the evidence affirming the contextual nature of leadership. It holds significant implications for improving the theoretical understanding of diverse leadership styles, considering the underdeveloped nations' context. Regarding policy implications, our study suggests that examining the relationships among dynamic leadership styles enhances comprehension of how complex organisations operate in a changing global business environment. Furthermore, employees may recognise and endorse the perceived leadership style, providing feedback to the organisation's management, which could improve the execution of the leadership strategy and ultimately aid in achieving the organisation's desired goals.

Although the study employed a random sampling technique to collect data, certain limitations remain when generalising the findings. With a relatively small sample size (305), this study was conducted mainly in Dhaka city and focused on private sector organisations in Bangladesh. Subsequent studies should increase the respondent count countrywide to generalise the findings to a broader community. Future studies should also examine how demographic factors affect leadership outcomes directly and indirectly.

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Conflict of Interest

The Authors hereby declare no conflict of interest.

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